

Singapore Experience in the Fight against Corruption

Zohidov Azamat A'zamovich¹

¹ Doctor of economics, professor

Annotation:

The article focuses on the Singapore experience in the fight against corruption. The article is a scientific study of the history and today's practice of fighting corruption and corrupt crimes in the country by the state of Singapore. Including the beginning of the initial reforms in the country, the reforms focus on the political will of the head of government and his experience in today's fight against corruption, legislative dispositions and sanctions, social issues carried out by the state in order to ensure the non-corruption of public services.

Keywords: corruption, crime, pay, bribe, reward, currency, banknotes, drug, bureaucracy, declamation.

In the fight against corruption, the countries of the Asia-Pacific region have their own experience. In particular, after Singapore achieved State independence in 1965, large-scale reforms began in the country. One of these is the anti-corruption reforms in this country. The state of Singapore was recognized as one of the economically "backward" states in the world before 1965. As a result of reforms led by Lee Kuan Yoo, who served as the country's prime minister from 1959-1990, the state of Singapore became one of the economically developed nations from the ranks of the economically backward states. Lee Kuan Yoo's famous phrase "start by locking up your three friends: you know exactly why, and they also know exactly why," has become one of the Chief principles of anti-corruption in the country. According to a 100-point assessment criterion based on the results of studies conducted by Transparency International, Singapore is among the least corrupt countries in the world. The political will of the government in organizing the fight against corruption in the country is seen in the excellence of anticorruption legislation as well as in the failure of an independent functioning anticorruption organization to be sold for bribes. In order to prevent corruption in the country, the government's monthly salaries of civil servants were increased several times. According to A.Solovev research conducted by, Singapore is among the countries with the

highest monthly salary for civil servants within the world States 11th place. That is, a civil servant was known to have an average salary of us \$ 3,388 per month, or an annual average of us \$ 45,384.

In order to improve the Anti-Corruption System in the state of Singapore, the Anti-Corruption Act was passed in 1960. The law defines anti-corruption mechanisms, anti-corruption principles, and the establishment of an independent Anti-Corruption Bureau in the country. In its activities, the bureau is entrusted with the authority to deal with corrupt situations in the activities of civil servants serving in high positions of power, to consider applications and complaints arising from corrupt situations in society. The bureau has the right to conduct an inquiry on any persons, including officials, serving in high positions. The director of the bureau is appointed by the president of the country, and in his activities he reports directly to the president. The bureau operates independently of police or other law enforcement agencies, ministries. The bureau is made up of Investigation, data processor and auxiliary departments. The investigation department is considered the most basic Department of the bureau and conducts investigative activities independently of other organizations. Completed cases are submitted to the prosecutor's office for legal action. The intelligence officers and auxiliary departments are responsible for selecting candidates, recommending them to government officials, and promoting them in positions.

Section III of the Act, known as "breach of law and punishment", establishes that Section 5 of the act-with the help of any person himself or others-soliciting, soliciting, receiving or receiving for himself in a corrupt form, or consenting for another person, giving, promising or offering to another person in the interests of the same person, is a corrupt crime. Also, for any salary or other reason for illegal promotion or reward, any person who stops any action or inaction in relation to any question or transaction proposed, in exchange for the encouragement of an official or service member working in the civil service of a question or a person participating in a transaction that must be executed is found to be the perpetrator of the A fine of \$ 100,000 (about US \$ 80,000) or A sentence of 5 years ' imprisonment has been set to apply to both sentences. The section on the presumption of corruption in certain circumstances of the Act provides that any unlawful pay has been paid, secured, or received by the government or persons working in any office or public body in any court case against a person for infringement provided for in Section 5 or 6 of the act, such a reward is considered to have been paid or received by the government, either on behalf of a person or on behalf of an agent, by a person who has or seeks to have any relationship with his office or any public body, and is perceived as an incentive or reward, as mentioned above. It has been established that the opposite must be proven if there is no case from this.

Section IV of the act defined the rights and powers of the bureau's director and staff, giving the bureau's director and his co-workers the authority to imprison individuals without a warrant over any identified corruption cases. When the criminal law of the state of Singapore was analyzed, it became known that the country's Criminal Code also contained a number of articles on the fight against the foreign economy. Including Section IX of the Criminal Code(crimes committed by or against civil servants), articles 161(awards received in addition to the legally received reward of a civil servant), 162(receiving a reward in exchange for corrupt or illegal influence on a civil servant), 163(receiving a reward for personal influence on a civil servant), 165(receiving any valuables from, Article 185(sale or purchase of real estate for sale under the authority of a civil servant), Section XI-(false evidence and crimes against a public court) 213(giving gifts to remove a criminal from punishment), 214-(giving gifts in the restoration of property related to the investigation of violations), articles 215-(receiving gifts in the return of stolen property), section XII-(falsification of the state seal) make), 257-(preparation or sale of instruments for falsification of the state stamp), 258-(sale of counterfeit state stamp), XIV-(crimes directed against public safety, health, tranquility and morality) Section, 272-(falsification of drinks and food prepared for sale), 273-(sale of harmful food and beverages), 274-(falsification of drugs), 275-(sale of counterfeit drugs), 276-(sale of any

drugs or other drugs in place), 292-(sale of sale of uncensored books), articles, section XVII(crimes directed against property) , Section 413(sale of stolen property), XVIII-(documents, electronic records, false documents and crimes in the field of currency and banknotes), section 464-(preparation of false documents or electronic records), 467-(forgery of securities or wills), 473A-(preparation and storage of equipment for making false instruments), 489a-(forgery of currency or banknotes), 489V-(use of counterfeit currency or banknotes as real currency or banknotes), 489s-(storage of counterfeit currency or banknotes), 489g-(making changes to the appearance of the currency in order to transfer it as another currency), Articles such as 489i-(possession of a modified currency) set out dispositions as well as sanctions, which are the basis for the fight against a foreign exchange economy.

In the opinion of the A.Manukyan and T. Khodjiyev, in operating without corruption in Singapore, it was reported that the most effective master directions were determined by the head of the county. That is, the creation of modern anti-corruption legislation, the establishment of a special, maximally independent state body to combat corruption, strengthening criminal liability measures for corruption crimes, establishing high-level social guarantees for state and Municipal Employees, constant and systematic replacement of management personnel, establishing legislative guarantees for the safety of the person and family members who testified on the fact of corruption, , independent examination of cases resulting from the consequences of corruption, responsibility of both parties in relations of corruption, differentiation of public and private interests, equality of all before the law and court, minimization of bureaucracy and document circulation in the state management apparatus, increase of the position of the monk based on personal information, personal services and achievements, not family or friendly ties, , master directions such as the introduction of a prosecutor's audit of banks, shares and accounts of those suspected of involvement in corrupt operatives were prescribed.

Literatures:

1. «Титан истории: международная реакция на кончину экс-премьера Сингапура Ли Куан Ю». <https://tass.ru/mezhdunarodnaya-panorama/1847163>
2. Transparency International “Индекс восприятия коррупции 2019”., <https://www.transparency.org/ru/news/cpi-2019-global-highlights#>
3. Соловьев. А.“Насколько хорошо за границей или Средние зарплаты в мире”., <https://visasam.ru/emigration/vybor/srednya-zarplata-v-mire.html>
4. “Закон о предотвращении коррупции”, 15 марта 1993 г. Часть I, Часть II (Назначение персонала и кадровые вопросы)., <https://sso.agc.gov.sg/Act/PCA1960>
5. “Закон о предотвращении коррупции”, 15 марта 1993 г., Часть III (нарушения и наказания, наказание за коррупцию)., ст-5 <https://sso.agc.gov.sg/Act/PCA1960>
6. “Закон о предотвращении коррупции”, 15 марта 1993 г., Часть III (Презумпция коррупции в определенных случаях)., <https://sso.agc.gov.sg/Act/PCA1960>
7. “Закон о предотвращении коррупции”, 15 марта 1993 г., Часть IV (Полномочия ареста и расследования)., <https://sso.agc.gov.sg/Act/PCA1960>
8. Манукян А. Ходжиев Т. “Антикоррупционная стратегия Сингапура: ориентация на результат”., Электрон журнал, “Трибуна молодого ученого”., ст.-118., <http://ehd.mgimo.ru/IORManagerMgimo/file?id=2B7F867E-CD39-4B6F-1DD1-00CD1CA09C5B>